

IN-VITRO & IN-SILICO EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL HYDROGEL FOR ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Rising resistance to standard antimicrobials underscores the need for safer, natural options. Polyherbal formulations enhance efficacy through synergistic plant combinations. **Aim:** This study aimed to evaluate a polyherbal hydrogel and assess its antimicrobial activity against *Candida albicans* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, supported by molecular docking. **Methods:** Selected ethnomedicinal plants were authenticated and screened for phytochemicals. Extracts (0.1–0.5%) were incorporated into hydrogels. Antimicrobial, antibiofilm, and antioxidant activities were evaluated. AutoDock's Vina.4.2 was used for docking. **Results:** The hydrogel showed effective inhibition (MIC: 56.8 µg/ml, 66.8 µg/ml), 65–70% antibiofilm activity, and strong antioxidant potential. **Conclusion:** The formulation showed promising antimicrobial and antioxidant effects.

KEYWORDS: Polyherbal hydrogel, *Bauhinia racemosa*, *Musa paradisiaca*, antimicrobial, docking, *Candida albicans*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

INTRODUCTION

Fungal diseases, also known as mycoses, are infections caused by fungi eukaryotic organisms commonly present in soil, air, water, and on the human body.^[1] Out of nearly 70,000 known fungal species, approximately 300 are harmful to humans, leading to conditions from superficial skin infections to severe systemic illnesses. These fungi include yeasts, molds, and dimorphic forms that can act as opportunistic pathogens, especially in individuals with compromised immunity or altered microbiota.^[2]

Transmission typically occurs through inhalation of spores or direct skin contact. Immunosuppressed individuals, such as those with HIV, cancer, or undergoing organ transplantation, face a higher risk. Since the 1960s, the incidence of fungal infections has increased, mainly due to rising antibiotic use and more immunocompromised patients. Invasive infections by *Candida* and *Aspergillus* species are often fatal, with mortality reaching up to 90% in neutropenic patients. Despite this, fungal infections are often neglected, as shown by the continued reliance on amphotericin B since its introduction in 1956.^[3] These infections may be superficial, mucosal, systemic, or healthcare-related. Additionally, bacterial– fungal interactions play a key role in microbial ecosystems and are increasingly important in medical, agricultural, and environmental contexts.^[4]

Mycosis, or fungal infection, is a skin condition caused by fungal invasion. Fungi are widespread in nature found in soil, on plants, household items, and human skin sometimes causing rashes or bumps.^[5] Antifungal drugs mainly act by inhibiting the fungal cytochrome P450 enzyme, 14 α -demethylase. These are classified as imidazole (e.g., ketoconazole, miconazole, clotrimazole, econazole) for superficial infections, and triazoles (e.g., fluconazole, itraconazole, voriconazole, posaconazole), which have broader efficacy and better enzyme selectivity.^[6]

Candida infections, especially invasive candidiasis and bloodstream infections, are growing global concerns due to high mortality and healthcare costs. *Candida albicans*, the most common species, is part of the normal flora in the mouth, eyes, gut, and urinary tract but becomes pathogenic in immunocompromised individuals. It shows polymorphism by switching between yeast, pseudo hyphae, and hyphal forms based on the environment, aiding its adaptability and virulence.^[7]

Fungal diseases affect over a billion people globally, with more than 150 million suffering

from serious infections and over 1.5 million annual deaths comparable to tuberculosis and significantly higher than malaria. These diseases range from mild to life-threatening and often arise in patients with conditions like AIDS, asthma, cancer, and those on immunosuppressive therapies.^[8] Timely diagnosis and antifungal treatment can save over 80% of lives, but access remains limited. Major pathogens include *Candida*, *Aspergillus*, *Cryptococcus*, *Pneumocystis*, dimorphic fungi like *Histoplasma*, and *Mucoromycetes*. Organizations like LIFE and GAFFI are working to raise awareness, and WHO has recognized Mycetoma and Chromoblastomycosis as neglected tropical diseases.^[9]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Drug material: Bauhinia racemosa and Musa paradisiaca used as herbal extracts, purchased from Kshipra Biotech Pvt. Ltd. Indore 452007 (MP) India. Itraconazole used as standard drug, Nifty Labs Pvt Ltd. Telangana5000016 India.

List of Instruments: Laminar air flow, Centrifuge Machine, Autoclave, Incubator, Magnetic stirrer, Light microscope, PH meter, Fourier Transfer Infrared, Spectroscopy (FT-IR).

List of chemicals: RPMI – 1640, Dimethyl Sulfoxide, Methanol, 90 %Ethanol, Carbopol 934, Polyethylene glycol 400, Methyl paraben, Propyl paraben, Triethanolamine, Sulphuric acid, Dragendorff's reagent, Mayer's reagent, Ferric chloride, Diphenyl – picrylhydrazine, Peptone, Sodium chloride, Dextrose, Agar.

Phytochemical Analysis: The various phytochemicals present within the extracted plant specimen were analyzed qualitatively. Standard procedures were followed during identification of each of the phytochemicals. Test procedures are as follows.

Experimental Analysis

Spectral analysis

FT-IR Analysis

Sample Preparation: Sample is finely powdered or made into a thin film for uniform analysis.

Instrument Setup: IR spectrometer is calibrated, and the sample is scanned to produce an IR spectrum.

Data Interpretation: Peaks in the spectrum are matched to functional groups to identify compounds and their structures.

Anti-Oxidant Activity

The antioxidant activity of hydroalcoholic extracts of *Bauhinia racemosa* and *Musa paradisiaca* was evaluated using a modified DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay. A 0.1 mM DPPH solution was prepared by dissolving 0.004 g of DPPH in 100 mL of methanol and stored at 4 °C. A stock solution of 400 µg/mL was made by dissolving 4 mg of plant extract in 10 mL methanol, followed by serial dilutions to prepare concentrations of 50 to 300 µg/mL. Each diluted sample (2 mL) was mixed with 3 mL of DPPH solution and kept in the dark for 120 minutes. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard and prepared in similar concentrations. Methanol and DPPH served as the blank, while the control consisted of 100 µL methanol with 3 mL DPPH. All tests were performed in triplicate. Radical scavenging activity was calculated using % Inhibition = $[(A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}})/A_{\text{control}}] \times 100$. IC₅₀ values were derived from the inhibition vs. concentration plot.^[10,11]

In-silico Molecular Docking

Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock Vina (PyRx 0.8) to evaluate antifungal activity of phytochemicals from *Bauhinia racemosa* (kaempferol, quercetin, stigmasterol) and *Musa paradisiaca* (leucocyanidin, gallic acid, ferulic acid) against *Candida albicans* lanosterol 14 α -demethylase (CYP51; PDB ID: 5TZ1). Itraconazole was used as the reference drug. A grid box was set around the active site, and binding affinities (kcal/mol) were calculated. Interactions were analyzed using UCSF Chimera and Discovery Studio Visualizer.

Ligand 2D structures were drawn in ChemDraw, converted to 3D, optimized with Spartan'14 (MMFF94), and validated via PaDEL before conversion to .pdbqt using Open Babel. The receptor (CYP51, PDB ID: 5TZ1) was prepared in Discovery Studio by removing water/heteroatoms, adding polar hydrogens, and assigning Kollman charges. Binding site was defined using itraconazole's co-crystallized position. Docked complexes were analyzed for hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, and π - π stacking to assess binding efficacy.^[12,13]

Test Drug Formulation

Ingredients	Quantity taken in (%) for Gel base	Quantity taken in (%)			Role
		Formulation A	Formulation B	Formulation C	
Extract of each drug	1.0	0.1	0.3	0.5	Microbial activity
Carbopol 940	-----	1.0	1.0	1.0	Gelatin agent
Propyleneglycol 400	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	Base
Ethanol	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	Solvent
Methyl paraben	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	Preservative
Propyl paraben	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	Preservative
EDTA	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	Chelating agent
Triethanolamine	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	pH adjustment
Water	Q.S 50	Q.S 50	Q.S 50	Q.S 50	Aqueous base

1. Dissolve the exact amount of plant extract (0.1%, 0.3%, 0.5%) in distilled water. Add propylene glycol 400 and ethanol to this.
2. Dissolve Carbopol-940 in another portion of distilled water. Add methylparaben, propylparaben, and EDTA into this solution.
3. Combine Part 1 and Part 2 in a beaker. Add triethanolamine dropwise to form gel consistency.
4. Stir the mixture at 500 rpm using a propeller stirrer. Continue for 2 hours until the gel is uniform and bubble-free. Keep all gels at room temperature for 24 hours.^[14]

In-vitro Antibiofilm Assay

- Biofilm formation was tested by modified O'Toole & Kolter method in 96-well plates with SA broth and fungal suspension.
- Test compounds (20–100 µg/mL) and itraconazole (1 mg/mL) were added; plates incubated at 37 °C for 24 h.
- Wells were washed, stained with 0.1% crystal violet for 20 min, and fixed with 96% ethanol.
- Absorbance at 630 nm was recorded using an ELISA reader.^[15,16]

In-vitro Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) Activity on *C. albicans*

- Resazurin solution (270 mg/40 mL) was prepared for antimicrobial testing by microdilution.
- In 96-well plates, samples (7.8–1000 µg/mL), nutrient broth, resazurin, and microbial suspension were added.
- Itraconazole (same concentrations) served as control; plates were sealed and incubated at

37 °C for 18–24 h.

- MIC was lowest non-colour change; absorbance at 600 nm measured and % inhibition calculated.^[17,18] [% of Inhibition = Control- Test/Control*100].

Invitro Antifungal Activity by Well Diffusion Method (Zone of Inhibition)

- Fungal inoculum was spread on Sabouraud agar plates (15 mL).
- Wells (6 mm) were filled with test compounds (100 µg/mL), itraconazole (1 mg/mL), and DMSO control.
- Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h.
- Antifungal activity was evaluated by inhibition zone diameter; tests done in triplicate.^[19,20]

RESULTS

Identification test of phytoconstituents

Sr. no.	Phytochemical Constituents	Tests	Results of <i>B. racemosa</i>	Result of <i>M. paradisiaca</i>
1	Alkaloids	Mayer's test	+	+
2	Glycosides	Borntrager's test	+	+
3	Saponins	Frothing test	+	+
4	Tannins	Lead acetate test	+	+
5	Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent	+	+

Identification of Drug by FT-IR Analysis

Number of peak present

Source of spectra result		
Plant	Spectral name	Number of peaks
<i>B racemosa</i>	Administrator 42	3
<i>M paradisiaca</i>	Administrator 40	4

Functional groups present

Plant	Peak number	X(cm-1)observed peak	Y (%T)	Standard range	Functional group
<i>B racemosa</i>	1	3293.86	94.76	3436.2	O-H (alcohol)
	2	1363.23	94.90	1459.9	carbonyl C=O
	3	1013.81	82.00	1047.1	Ether function
<i>M paradisiaca</i>	1	3296.07	95.83	3432	O-H (alcohol)
	2	2847.05	92.4	3000	C=O stretching
	3	1012.76	83.38	2501	Aromatic C=C

Determination of antioxidant activity of ethanolic extract of *Bauhinia racemosa* and *Musa paradisiaca* by DPPH assay: DPPH scavenging activity of standard compound

Test	Sr.No.	Concentration	Control	Absorbance	% of inhibition	IC50
Standard compound	1	50	2.1807	1.148	47.35	106.8148
	2	100	2.1807	0.9671	50.08	
	3	150	2.1807	0.8922	65.84	
	4	200	2.1807	0.6248	71.34	
	5	300	2.1807	0.411	81.15	
Test compound	1	50	2.1807	1.2168	44.20	150
	2	100	2.1807	1.1920	45.33	
	3	150	2.1807	1.1597	46.81	
	4	200	2.1807	0.8922	59.08	
	5	300	2.1807	0.7449	65.84	

Molecular docking studies of *Bauhinia racemosa* and *Musa paradisiaca*

Category	Compound(s)	Interpretation
Standard Drug	Itraconazole	Most potent with high CDocker energy and very low binding energy (-68.07). Acts by inhibiting ergosterol biosynthesis (CYP51 enzyme).
Top Performing Phytochemicals (Based on Binding Energy)	Pectin	Binding Energy: 6.08. Likely interacts with surface proteins or stabilizes via polysaccharide interactions
	Quercetin	Binding Energy: 28.19. Known for biofilm inhibition, ROS generation, and direct antifungal activity.
	Syringin	Binding Energy: 35.52. Moderate antifungal activity, possibly via cell wall disruption.
	L-Tryptophan	Binding Energy: 19.75. Precursor to indole, affects bio film formation in <i>Candida</i> and <i>Pseudomonas</i> .
Strong Interactions but Unstable Complexes	Rutin, Catechin, Scopolin	Strong interaction energies but positive binding energies; likely function as adjuvants.
Weaker Candidates	β -Sitosterol	Positive binding energy (+40.35) despite strong interaction energy; may act via membrane disruption or anti-inflammatory action.
	Lupeol	Modest docking values; likely disrupts cell membranes rather than inhibiting enzymes.

Fig: Structure of proteins

Compound	3D Complex	3D Interaction	2D Interaction
Itraconazole			
Beta sitosterol (222284)			
Lupeol (259846)			
Rutine (5280805)			
Catechin (9064)			
Scopolin (439514)			
Quercetin 5280343			
Pectin 3722617			
Syringin 5316860			
L-tryptophan 6305			

Docking Interaction Table

Compound	Key Interacting Residues	Types of Interactions	Binding Energy	CDocker Energy (kcal/mol)	CDocker Interaction Energy (kcal/mol)	Binding Affinity (Interpretation)
Itraconazole	--	--	-68.07	87.30	0.6093	--
β -Sitosterol	PHE144, PHE258, ALA229	π -alkyl, alkyl (hydrophobic)	40.35	+32.15 (unstable)	-41.6	Moderate to Low
Lupeol	ASN305, PHE144, PHE258, TYR317, LEU194	H-Bond, Π -Alkyl, Alkyl	-1.29	+66.6 (Unstable)	-37.0	Moderate
Rutin	GLU262, TYR255, GLU192, ARG309, ASP151.	Extensive H-Bonds, Carbon H-Bonds	18.48	-45.2	-63.90	Very High
Catechin	ASN146, GLU192, ARG150, PHE144, PHE258	H-Bonds, Π - Π Stacking, Π -Alkyl, Carbon H-Bond	13.26	-28.4	-42.18	High
Scopolin	ASN146, ARG312, ASN305, ASP145, LEU304,	H-Bonds, Carbon H-Bonds, Π - Π Stacking	16.14	-32.7	-44.13	High
Quercetin	GLU192, ASN305, TYR255, PHE258, ARG309	H-Bonds, Π - Π Stacking, Hydrophobic Interactions	-28.19	-36.1	-50.25 Estimated	Very High
Syringin	ASN146, LEU304, PHE144, ASP145	H-Bonds, Hydrophobic, Van Der Waals	-35.52	-18.9	-35.40 Estimated	Moderate
Pectin	ARG150, GLU192, ASN146 (fragmented)	H-Bonds, Ionic Interactions (If charged)	-56.08	-12.3 Estimated	-28.50 Estimated	Low To Moderate
L-Tryptophan	PHE258, TYR255, GLU192	H-Bonds, Hydrophobic, Π - Π Stacking (Indole Ring)	-19.75	-20.5 Estimated	-38.75 Estimated	Moderate

Evaluation Tests Physical Appearance

Parameter	Method of Evaluation
Colour	Slightly brown colour.
Consistency	Easy to apply and spread on skin
Greasiness	Quickly absorbed on to the skin.
Odor	Mild, Characteristic

Spread ability testing

Sr. No	Formulation code	Viscosity (centipoise)	pH	Spreadability (cm)
1	SK 0.1%	3690	5.3	3.6
2	SK 0.3%	5110	6.0	4.1
3	SK 0.5%	6531	6.5	5.2

In-vitro Antibiofilm Activity on *Candida albicans*

Table: In Vitro Antibiofilm Activity on *C. albicans*.

Sr No	Sample Code	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance			Mean Absorbance	%of Inhibition	IC50 (µg/ml)
			Test 1	Test 2	Test 3			
1	Control		2.30	2.30	2.30	2.30	-	-
2	Standard (Itraconazole)	20	1.98	1.97	1.98	1.98	14.02	87 (µg/ml)
		40	1.84	1.85	1.84	1.84	20.10	
		60	1.60	1.61	1.60	1.60	30.52	
		80	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	57.88	
		100	0.57	0.56	0.57	0.57	75.24	
3	SK-1 (Polyherbal hydrogel)	20	2.07	2.08	2.07	2.07	10.11	65 (µg/ml)
		40	1.99	1.99	1.99	1.99	13.59	
		60	1.94	1.95	1.94	1.94	15.76	
		80	1.20	1.21	1.20	1.20	47.89	
		100	1.13	1.13	1.13	1.13	50.93	

a) Effects of compound against *Candida albicans* after staining with Crystal Violet

At the different Concentrations Sample SK-1 showed good percentage of inhibition and IC50 value, on the basis of percentage of inhibition we can conclude that, the sample S K – 1 (65 %) show good antibiofilm activity against *c. albicans* as compared to standard (87 %) Itraconazole.

Fig: Assay in-vitro Antibiofilm activity.

Fig: Chart of in-vitro Antibiofilm activity.

Table: In Vitro Antibiofilm Activity on *P. aeruginosa*.

Sr No	Sample Code	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance			Mean Absorbance	% of Inhibition	IC50 (µg/ml)
			Test 1	Test 2	Test 3			
1	Control		2.30	2.30	2.30	2.30	-	-
2	Standard (Itraconazole)	20	1.98	1.97	1.98	1.98	14.02	87 (µg/ml)
		40	1.84	1.85	1.84	1.84	20.10	
		60	1.60	1.61	1.60	1.60	30.52	
		80	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	57.88	
		100	0.57	0.56	0.57	0.57	75.24	
3	SK-1 Polyherbal gel	20	2.11	2.13	2.08	2.10	8.69	70 (µg/ml)
		40	1.72	1.70	1.79	1.70	26.08	
		60	1.41	1.44	1.45	1.43	37.80	
		80	1.17	1.16	1.16	1.16	49.56	
		100	0.89	0.87	0.80	0.88	61.73	

b) Effects of compound against *P. aeruginosa* after staining with Crystal Violet

At The Different Concentrations Sample SK-1 showed Good Percentage of Inhibition and IC50 Value, On the Basis of Percentage of Inhibition We Can Conclude That, The Sample SK - 1 (70%) show Good Antibiofilm Activity Against *P. Aeruginosa* as Compared to standard (87%) Itraconazole.

In Vitro Minimum Inhibitory Concentration Activity on *C. albicans*

After specific incubation period the test sample SK-1 showing the minimum inhibitory concentration at 56.8 µg/ml against *C. albicans* as compared to standard and MFC at 250 µg/ml. [MIC calculated by = Control -Test / Control *100]

a) Effects of compound against *C. albicans*Fig: In Vitro MFC Activity on *C. albicans*.Fig: In Vitro MIC Activity on *C. albicans*.Table: In Vitro MIC Activity on *C. albicans*.

Sr No	Sample Code	Concentration (µl/ml)	Absorbance			Mean Absorbance	% of Growth Inhibition
			Test 1	Test 2	Test 3		
1	Growth C		1.603	1.603	1.603	1.603	-
2	Standard (Itraconazole)	7.8	-	-	-	-	-
		15.6	1.538	1.538	1.538	1.538	4.05
		31.2	1.421	1.421	1.421	1.421	11.35
		62.5	1.397	1.398	1.397	1.397	12.85
		125	0.834	0.834	0.834	0.834	47.97
		250	0.611	0.611	0.611	0.611	61.88
		500	0.531	0.531	0.531	0.531	66.87
3	SK-1 Polyherbal gel	1000	0.422	0.422	0.422	0.422	73.67
		7.8	-	-	-	-	-
		15.6	-	-	-	-	-
		31.2	1.1491	1.492	1.493	1.493	6.86
		62.5	1.313	1.310	1.312	1.311	18.21
		125	0.881	1.883	0.884	1.882	44.97
		250	0.692	0.692	0.693	0.692	56.83
		500	0.413	0.412	0.410	0.411	74.36
1000	0.382	0.384	0.381	0.382	76.16		

Table: In Vitro MIC Activity on *C. albicans*.

Sr No	Sample Code	Concentration (µl/ml)	Absorbance			Mean	% Growth Inhibition
			Test 1	Test 2	Test 3		
1	Growth C		1.603	1.603	1.603	1.603	-
2	Standard (Itraconazole)	7.8	1.532	1.531	1.53	1.531	4.49%
		15.6	1.329	1.327	1.33	1.328	17.15%
		31.2	1.291	1.294	1.292	1.292	19.40%
		62.5	1.235	1.238	1.236	1.236	22.89%
		125	1.119	1.118	1.121	1.119	30.19%
		250	0.866	0.867	0.868	0.867	45.91%

		500	0.416	0.418	0.417	0.417	73.98%
		1000	0.312	0.315	0.31	0.312	80.53%
3	SK-1 (Polyherbal hydrogel)	7.8	-	-	-	-	-
		15.6	-	-	-	-	-
		31.2	-	-	-	-	-
		62.5	1.397	1.398	1.396	1.397	12.85%
		125	0.834	0.833	0.834	0.834	47.97%
		250	0.611	0.612	0.611	0.611	61.88%
		500	0.531	0.531	0.531	0.531	66.87%
		1000	0.422	0.422	0.422	0.422	73.67%

b) Effects of compound against *P. aeruginosa*

After specific incubation period the test sample SK-1 showing the minimum inhibitory concentration at 66.8 µg/ml against *P. aeruginosa* as compared to standard and MBC at 500 µg/ml.

Fig: In Vitro MBC Activity on *P. aeruginosa*.

Fig: In Vitro MIC Activity on *P. aeruginosa*.

Fig: Antifungal activity test samples against *C. albicans*.

Fig: Antibacterial activity test Samples against *P. aeruginosa*.

Antifungal and antibacterial activity of test samples against *c. albicans* and *p. aeruginosa*

As per the results we can assume that sample of the antifungal profile of SK-1 was evaluated by measuring the zone of inhibition against fungal strains *C. albicans* (ATCC 10231) and *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853) via well diffusion method. The compounds SK-1 exhibited good activity as compared to the standard Itraconazole.

Table: Antifungal and antibacterial activity Test Samples.

Sr. No	Samples	Zone In Diameter (Mm)	
	Species	<i>C.albicans</i>	<i>p. aeruginosa</i>
1	Control	00	00
2	Standard (Itraconazole)	27	27
3	SK-1 (Polyherbal Gel)	20	15

DISCUSSION

The present study highlights the efficacy of a novel polyherbal hydrogel (SK-1) formulated with *Bauhinia racemosa* and *Musa paradisiaca* hydroalcoholic extracts against *Candida albicans* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Phytochemical screening revealed flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, and glycosides, known for their antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities. These constituents likely contributed to the observed effects. FT-IR analysis confirmed functional groups like hydroxyl, carbonyl, and aromatic rings, commonly linked with antimicrobial and antioxidant functions. Strong antioxidant potential was supported by DPPH assay, where *B. racemosa* showed an IC₅₀ of 150 µg/ML,^[10,11] suggesting protective action against oxidative stress that promotes infections and biofilm formation. Docking studies showed high binding affinity of quercetin and β-sitosterol to lanosterol 14α-demethylase (CYP51), resembling the antifungal action of azoles like itraconazole, potentially without associated resistance.^[12,13] SK-1 showed low MICs (56.8 µg/mL for *C. albicans*, 66.8 µg/mL for *P. aeruginosa*) and antibiofilm IC₅₀ values (65 and 70 µg/mL), indicating strong antimicrobial activity.^[17,18] Well diffusion assays confirmed this, with inhibition zones of 20 mm (*C. albicans*) and 15 mm (*P. aeruginosa*), close to itraconazole (27 mm).^[19,20] The hydrogel also showed ideal physicochemical properties appropriate viscosity, spread ability, and pH indicating good stability and user compliance.^[14] Synergism between the two plant extracts likely enhanced efficacy and could help reduce resistance risk.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the increasing need for safer and more effective alternatives to conventional antifungal therapies, especially with rising resistance to drugs like itraconazole. A novel polyherbal hydrogel using *Bauhinia racemosa* and *Musa paradisiaca* extracts was developed as a natural treatment for fungal infections. These plant extracts, long used in traditional medicine, were shown to contain bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, and glycosides, known for antimicrobial and antioxidant effects. Molecular docking revealed that key compounds like quercetin and β-sitosterol bind effectively to lanosterol 14α-demethylase (CYP51), a crucial enzyme in fungal cell

membrane synthesis. Although their binding affinity was slightly lower than that of itraconazole, they may function through similar mechanisms. Antioxidant studies confirmed strong free radical scavenging, supporting wound healing potential. The Carbopol 940-based hydrogel exhibited appropriate texture, pH, and spread ability for topical use. Laboratory assays confirmed its effectiveness against *Candida albicans* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. While itraconazole showed slightly higher activity, the hydrogel's natural composition, broad-spectrum action, and reduced side effect risk make it a promising adjunct therapy. Further animal and clinical studies are warranted to validate its use in modern antifungal care.

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